

The Nembe Middleman, Warfare and Diplomacy in Pre-Colonial Nigeria

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Abstract

The Pre-colonial Nigerian area was characterized by regional trade zones that fed the different culture zones through a sophisticated mechanism referred as the Delta Middleman trade. In an era when the canoe was the chief means of transportation, the mercantile class dominated the regional political economy, traversed, distributed, organized, standardized, regulated as well as facilitated the movement of goods and services across borders. As a result, the middleman established many arteries of relations with other regions that were mutually beneficial to all. This study argues that utilizing the benefits of the policy of the ‘trust system’ as principle of trade was a major structural innovation arising from the capital flow into markets traditionally short of capital. It was this capital the middlemen manipulated to control the demand and supply chain of intermediaries; in a manner that created artificial scarcity of products and maximized profits for him. The study further highlights that, for economic considerations, Europeans sought means of breaking the Delta middleman trade that was eventually broken in 1857. The study also stressed that trust was the common practice of credit selling in regional trade, and that, the Europeans presence only expanded its scope which was referred to as the ‘trust system’. Thus, the idea of a complex trading system was not a new thing but the challenge of the introduction of ‘falsehood’, ‘double trust’ and ‘rascality’ that is new. However, it was the Western ‘falsehood’, ‘double trust’ and ‘rascality’ that changed the traditionally time-tested practices of warfare and diplomacy from “limited” to the European-infested “unlimited” scale warfare.

Background

The pre-colonial history of the Niger Delta was characterized by regional trade zones which essentially complemented one another. One common characteristic of the region's economy was the dominant role of middlemen. It is difficult to date the origin of the Nembe middleman relations, but it is probably of long standing. The Aro, Awka, Nri, Nkwerre, Abiriba are known to have traversed the region of the Delta hinterland over long periods of time. The river and creek routes have witnessed the activities of the Nembe, Kalabari, Bonny, Igala and Aboh for centuries before the imposition of colonial rule. It means that for centuries, inter-community trade existed in the Lower Niger. To cap it all, the Benue Valley was linked with the Lower Niger through the activities of the Delta middlemen. Thus, patterns of regional trade antedate the sixteenth century, and by the nineteenth century, it was well established.

The development and sustenance of these commercial relations on inter-territorial basis required the involvement of territorial agents. In practice, these agents were local brokers or middlemen of immense importance. The Igala-Aboh commercial relationship is a good example. In the Delta, the Nembe middleman trade with the mainland communities should not be overemphasized. The existence of local or indigenous middlemen suggests that regional trade was not without territorial challenges. In essence, these challenges amounted to attempts to defend spheres of influence. It is in this sense that some of the supposed conflicts were managed in diplomatic fashions. It is difficult to understand the absence of the diplomatic conflict in contemporary accounts without the issues behind them. It is however, known that spheres (markets) of influence were maintained and respected by other middlemen. It is probable that trade spheres were only demarcated after periods of trade rivalry and conflict.

Thus, the wars of the early period can be interpreted as reflections of trade rivalry. Kalabari and Nembe fought on the Orashi for the control of trade spheres. During the nineteenth century, the friendship between the Kalabari and Nembe ceased when the Kalabari began to seek new oil markets north-westwards up the Orashi River "into

territory claimed by Nembe as her exclusive commercial preserve” (Alagoa, 1982:143). However, because the two groups are linked by kinship, the management of the conflicts and resolution was aptly linked to idea of brotherhood and soon peace was restored between warring factions, as if nothing had happened.

Essentially, a major factor in the continued participation of Nembe middleman in commerce was Nigeria’s geographical location. The geographical environment facilitated the movement of goods and peoples from one place to another, and assigned a natural division of labour to the culture zones. Thus to Jones (1963:134), “neither the Eastern Delta nor the hinterlands were self-sufficient in the economy. He therefore asserts that the hinterland lacked salt and protein, and their nearest supply was the Niger Delta”.

On the basis of these inter-relations, the neighbours were identified as specialized communities. It was the thinking that informed Afigbo’s assertion (1980:122) that “the links that bind the people of the two culture zones are as ancient, deep and varied; and therefore, as important as the links internal to each group”.

Corroborative evidence suggests that by the sixteenth century, trade with the hinterland and the Delta communities was already in an advanced state (Kimble, 1937:128-132). Over the centuries, Nembe middlemen (merchants) developed and sustained relationship with communities along this important Niger waterway. The Niger, of course, had been a super highway for centuries and a major artery for economic and political expression. The control of the Niger routes and markets was a crucial aspect of Delta diplomacy. The formulation of fictive kinship ties and socio-religious affinities with hinterland communities served economic interests. Nembe and other Delta middlemen created indigenous accounts of common origin and cultural affinities to ensure their safe passage to markets in distant lands. It was through this rigorous pattern or clime that hinterland produced reached the Delta, through chains of intermediaries in the same way as goods of European manufacture as well as Delta produce reached the hinterland markets controlled by the middlemen. It is therefore apt to have an idea of what the middlemen means in other to

comprehend his functions in the patterns of trade and commercial linkages outlined above.

The Concept or Idea of Middleman

The English dictionary defines middleman as an intermediary, agent between two (or more) parties or an intermediate dealer between the manufacturer and the retailer or customer. Therefore, the development and sustenance of commercial relations on inter-territorial basis required the involvement of territorial agents, called the middleman, as we have established previously in the study. The equivalent concept of middleman in the Nembe view are Tubokonbo, Tubo-nongu, Tubo-na-alabo¹.

The middleman mechanism can be seen in the vital role it regulates in commercial relations in the pre-colonial society. In practice, these agents were middlemen of immense importance. Corroborating the above Alagoa noted that, the Nembe and her hinterland commercial relationship is a good example of sustained middleman activity in long distance trade (Alagoa, 1976:331-372).

There is a plethora of writing on the concept or idea of a middleman. The convergence or consensus is self-explanatory. The Nembe middleman has similar roles he plays as elsewhere. There existed a mercantile class tubo-nongu merchants chiefs traversing the entire Delta region as itinerant traders, facilitating the exchange of the Delta goods and services, and oftentimes, cultural exchanges. This basically means they are the medium through which exchanges between the two geographical zones could address issues of scarcity or what each group could produce with respect to environmental factors or geographical division of labour. For example, they supplied the fish and salt as well as other aquatic products to the people of mainland and also brought food, livestock, slaves etc, to the Delta. It was a world of interdependence, as none of the geographical zones was self-sufficient.

¹ *Tubokonbo* means a trader, *Tubo-nongu* refers to a trading corporation while *Tubo-na-alabo* means a trading chief who is equivalent to the modern day entrepreneur.

In so doing, the Tubo-nongo had to organize fairs with the mainland to create centres of produce collection for market spheres. The middleman having created these fairs or nodal centres monopolized the trade of such markets, in most cases at the beach, hence the name “bench markets”. This was because the major commercial transaction of the whole trade was carried out on the riverside or sand bars. The middleman trading canoes would anchor at the beach where the trade merchandise was finally sorted out for delivery to the customers. For the Niger Igbo markets, Talbot (1969:172) wrote, “Aboh market was the greatest of them all attended by merchants from several places, particularly the Nembe”. This was done through trade which again was facilitated by the space economy of the middlemen.

Each city-state had its economic region, whose trade goods must pass through the hands of their middlemen traders. As a consequence, they maintained peace and order in these spheres of influence. Apparently, the aim was to ensure free flow of trade. The trade routes were secured so long as they kept the friendship of the powerful Nembe middlemen (Eferebo, 2013:261-262).

Also, the Tubo-nongu negotiated prices and enforced other trade regulations and conditions of trade at the ports and hinterland markets, at which they enforced codes of commercial conduct and marriage alliances in these communities in which the middleman cultural practices became very prestigious (Alagoa, 1995:5). The middleman did not only regulate trade but also provides loan or credit debt called Sa.² The Sa Mechanism facilitated and enhanced the trade; this practice was referred to as trust system. The trade between the Delta and its hinterland would have been difficult to conduct without a form of credit. It was normal for a Tubokonbo to raise the initial capital from personal savings or from family sources or even through borrowing processes known as igbogi boloi or safi³ (personal communications with Professor Adaye Orugbani 24th April, 2017 at Choba, Port Harcourt). Since the Delta trade

² Sa means debt in Nembe

³ Igbogi boloi means a borrowing from somebody while safi means indebtedness.

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largely depended on credit arrangement, credit worthiness was very important factor. In this sense, only the Tubo-nongu well introduced were likely to secure credit advances from the coastal brokers as stated. John Adams noted that very extensive credits were granted the coastal middlemen by the masters of European vessels in the 19th century (Dike, 1956:109-10). He however stated that this advance bound the middlemen traders to particular European vessels. The general secrets of the trade – was to discriminate properly in whom you place confidence. The system whereby goods were trusted to traders provided capital for European and African import merchants as principals and commission agents. The credit financing principle showed that the trust system was widespread (Newbury, 1972:86). While acknowledging that this was “a major structural innovation” arising from the produce trade, Newbury maintains that the “aggregate of exchanges” involved large scale of imports and represented capital flow in markets traditionally short of capital. In this sense, the middleman controlled the demand and supply chain, and as such could create artificial scarcity and maximize profit to sell to places of high demand and so forth.

It is important to note that, the general believed that only European traders advanced credit to the Delta middlemen. But this was not the case in all the time; Delta Chiefs and middlemen also advanced credit facilities to European traders. Chief Iwowari and Kalango were said to have advanced some European traders several cases or puncheon of palm oil to sell abroad on many occasions in the heyday of the staple trade on the Brass River (personal communications with Chief Allen Atangari Bugo 6th June 2002 at Nembe). Commenting on the vitality of the trust system, E.D. Morel has pointed out (Morel, 1968:78):

"Giving out trust is not invariably confined to the Europeans. Native chiefs have known to give trust to Europeans up to 1000 cases of palm oil, in days too When palm oil was worth 15 per puncheon. This would represent a credit of 15,000".

The Tubo-nongu would establish fictive kinship ties to maintain social and economic interests. It is important to note that the economy of Nembe (Delta) depended on the waterways and riverside markets, the middlemen and the traditional government adopted a policy that ensured free passage for Nembe traders. The communities on the Niger or Orashi routes could undermine the influence and power of Nembe by the closure of the waterways. The Nembe middlemen merchant oligarchy was capable of defending their commercial interest. It was the practice to own slaves as armed guards in trade canoes and as personal bodyguards for traders. Sometimes, slave camps were strategically positioned to safeguard economic zones and routes (Nzimiro, 1971: 140). At other times armed war-canoes escort the merchants for safety purposes. Since the Nembe state did not possess a standing army, the leading merchant-politician (chiefs) possessed private armies, as elsewhere in the Delta (personal communications with Professor Adaye Orugbani April, 24th 2017 at Choba, Port Harcourt). The Nembe state did not control the use of the private armies. Rather, a sort of alliance existed between the government and Tubo-nongu whereby the later utilized their armies in support of the state in return for government patronage. The state was thus the patron of the powerful merchant-politicians with their private armies.

It is therefore not surprising that the attendance of distant markets had its own risks. The formulation of kinship ties and marriage alliances along the main arteries of trade was a response to the insecurity which characterized the Lower Niger trade. It was the duty of Tubo-nongu to devise means of settling trade disputes, arranging his personal security and adapting to local political exigencies. Thus, the promotion of cultural affinities and political alliances was partly a function of middleman activities. With increased activities and accumulation of wealth, the Tubo-nongu became a merchant-politician, with vast control mechanisms in the state (as a chief - alabo), along the trade routes and markets.

The Tubo-nongu established diplomatic ties with several trade route communities or kingdoms not only for easy passage but also to secure commercial monopoly as far as the northern part of present-day Nigeria. According to Eferebo, the Nembe

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middlemen among other Delta traders travelled by canoes to Igala and Nupe where they traded with North African merchants at Lokoja, and Raba, an entrepot Nupe commercial centres on the Niger/Benue Rivers. The Nembe middlemen too, were said to be prominent and directly traded with the Igala, Igbira etc. at Lokoja. He however added that the articles of this trade include dried or smoked fish, crayfish, salt as well as other assorted aquatic seafoods in exchange for "kano cloth" (Ikagi beti in Nembe), leather goods, livestock and other agricultural products (Eferebo, 2013:25-26).

Also, the Nembe middlemen traders like other Deltans converge in these commercial towns and established diplomatic friendship with the host states. They made their friends agents as well as warehouses that stored produce for them. Consequently, they were always on the lookout for their Tubo-nongu friends to come along with lots of goods and gifts for them from the coast. The Nembe middlemen were known for trade rapport with their Hausa/Fulani customers in the Niger/Benue Rivers. Ama-Obari (2005:56-57) reports that some of their trade agents followed them to settle at Nembe, Such agents include Adamu Spiff, Gambo Mohammed etc, they later changed their names to Ada and Sambo, respectively to give themselves a new identity and help to proper assimilation and acculturation at their new home.

Supporting the evidence above, even as recent as the 19th century, the Lander Brothers were said to have observed North African and Hausa/Fulani merchants in league with the Delta middlemen trading on the Niger River. These foreign partners of the Delta middlemen merchants were frequenting the Niger estuary with local goods making profits for themselves and their Delta partners, especially the Nembe middlemen (Enemugwen, 2000:81).

Therefore, through these business associates and other linkages they established some level of diplomatic ties with the states of Igala, Wukari, Nupe, etc. on the upper Niger, Benue, Rima and Chad Basins. According to Eferebo (2013:29), "Igala kings always courted the friendship of the Delta states by sending slaves, elephant tusks, clothes and livestock to Nembe, Bonny, Okrika, Kalabari and Andoni regularly. To corroborate this evidence, in the 19th century the Lander Brothers were said to have

taken a small slave boy from the Igala king to the Bonny's king as gift item (Enemugwem, 2000:85).

Indeed, the Aro Igbo also established strong relations with the Nembe middleman. Their Awka brothers were not left out in this chain. They were suppliers of slaves and blacksmith works respectively. The Aro are friends of Nembe. They provided essential services such as trade goods, and also served as (TDR) conflict resolution experts on many occasions.

In general, the Tubo-nongu participated actively in the Sakoromo, the indigenous loan, credit or trust system of trade financing in their economic region. Indeed, the system remained the pivot of the Delta trade. The Nembe Tubo-nongu or brokers extended such European sponsored credits (trust) to their hinterland agents. This method helped to finance trade, but the risk of default was high (Eferebo, 2013:224-275).

The crisis of the last decade of the 19th century was basically that of economic adjustments for the Tubo-nongu. Their business declined when their four century monopoly was broken by European merchants (Royal Niger Company). While some Tubo-nongu preferred compromise with the white many others opposed it. One thing was however paramount in the new economic order that emerged in the 20th century, those who compromised with the 'white rulers' became the privileged ones (Alagoa, 1964:120). They were appointed warrant chiefs, native courts and native authority etc. So long as the Tubo-nongu concentrated on trade, the government would assist them. That is, depending on the interest of participation, the middleman derived remuneration from the colonial government. This was the case of the Nembe middleman.

Warfare and Diplomacy

Available evidence indicates that warfare has been a routine feature of the Delta social and economic existence. Visiting the area in the 15th century, Pereira wrote that the Delta people were warlike and their belligerence affected adversely the peace

of the region. The story was not different in the 19th century as evident in Baikie's accounts of conflicts and wars among the people (Baikie, 1856). The truth was that wars were fought, not as ends in themselves, but as means to specific economic and political ends. They were, in general, consequences built to the competitive search for fishing grounds in pre-European times; and later, as consequences of the "struggle for control" of markets or trade routes during the era of the overseas trade, as demonstrated previously in this study.

One incident worth discussing within the purview of the Niger Delta middleman conflict was that of "chopping of oil", and the problems associated with it (Dike, 1956:109-110). "Chopping of oil" simply means seizure of oil (and other produce) by one supercargo of oil belonging to another supercargo. This is because the Delta trade was fed on the extension of credit or Sakoromo by European trader to the Tubo-nongu who contacted his agent in the hinterland for oil which he would deliver to the European trader who had advanced him the credit. But "chopping" may occur when through pressure from another European trader the middleman sold the oil to another trader instead of the one who had advanced credit. Naturally, trouble arose the "chopping" of the oil. Similarly, the Nembe Tubo-nongu also took drastic measures against their agents when such betrayal occurred. The trust system also created a social category of people referred to "palm oil ruffians" who would take double trust from the Tubo-nongu for selfish ends. The Nembe middlemen would use their wealth and power to quash anything that would strangle trade such as the double trust phenomenon. According to Okorobia, Anyama, Otuogidi among others were attacked and destroyed by the armed merchants (Tubo-nongu) of Nembe who had entrusted goods to some unfaithful agents in these and other places.

In other conflict situation resulting from double trust or related vices the Tubo-nongu would give new names to such recalcitrant communities. Ebiwari stated that some were named after the prominent agents, while others were associated with objects produced in the towns. Otakeme and Otuogidi, for example, were re-christened "Ogidiama" (cutlass town), "Okpiniama" respectively. Similarly. Otukpesi and

Onuebum were renamed "Anyama" and Alagbafama" respectively, while Okodi became "Okodogu". The cases of Sagbama, Ekpetiama and Kaiama were not different as the former was renamed a trade measurement (ekpeti-box) for articles such as palm kernel, fufu and yago to the Nembe middlemen to standardize trade, meaning the town where the box was used for cheating (Olali, 2008:150 and Eferebo, 2013:195). While Ekpeinbiri became "Kagiama" as a result of double trust and adulteration of produce on the part of Tubo-nongu as cheats was corrupted to Kaiama (Owonaro, 1949:27) Meanwhile the name Sagbama came as a result of Sa owed the Nembe Tubo-nongu by the people of the area (Eferebo, 2013:199).

The 19th century was a delicate period for the Nembe middleman as elsewhere in Nigeria. People began to demand and receive double trust while in other climes they experimented with adulteration of produce and use of false measures. Falsehood came to be regarded as being smart and many became too cunning. Coupled with such social vices was the issue of routes closure thereby creating a new middlemanship. It therefore behooved on the Nembe middleman to destroy this "new order" "produce new men" and centres with new power and influence. The new men on their own part, amalgamated forces to protect their sovereignty, and waged wars against the Nembe middleman trade monopoly (Eferebo 2013:189-192).

Thus, the Nembe middleman influence was challenged in her Niger economic region, especially Onitsha, Asaba, Ossomari and Aboh. According to Alagoa, "the Nembe middleman had great influence at Aboh as a result of trade goods they brought from the Brass River" (Alagoa 1964: 86). Also, that King Amain (Nembe) married Obi Ossai's favourite daughter, Addizetta. She was the centerpiece of the Nembe middleman trade and maintained good relations for them. The cordial diplomatic ties established between them was the basis that the Obi of Aboh received the ransom of twenty slaves from King Amain to obtain the custody of the Landers at Aboh which brought fame and high diplomatic pedigree for the Nembe merchants. This incident made King Amain to be proud as his envoys sometimes claimed that King Amain was most powerful black ruler, as this was unacceptable to other rulers, particularly Obi

Ossai of Aboh. He intended to broke, the Nembe middleman by being hostile to King Amain, when Obi Ossai had tried to embroil him with the supercargoes by accusing King Amain of murdering an Englishman. This accordingly, scared him and fighting ensued eventually between citizens of the two friendly states. Apparently, the fine diplomatic friendship between them became sour as there were no Nembe Tubo-nongu sighted at Aboh. Baikie (1856:317-318) corroborated this account:

A quarrel, however, soon took place which ended in the Aboh people seizing the cargoes, and the Nimbe (Nembe) middlemen retreating and carrying off some Aboh canoes, since then friendly relations have been dropped, but a year before the arrival of the "pleiad" (Baikie's ship), two headmen had been dispatched to go to Nimbe to try and settle differences. But various diplomatic difficulties and delays had occurred, and when I heard the story, the Aboh envoys were still at the court of Nimbe. (emphasis mine)

Similarly, other economic regions or communities also acted in related ways to break the Nembe middleman by closing routes. Kaiama had gained prominence and attracted local and European traders to it in the mid-19th century. They therefore strongly opposed the penetration of the Nembe merchants from going up the Niger to trade with its traditional market spheres such as Aboh, Onitsha and Asaba. This measure was specifically designed to break their middleman monopoly. Kaiama like others, on account of its newly developed middleman traders barred the Nembe from the hinterland, forcing them to buy from its traders. In response, Nembe decided to take police action against the Kolokuma middleman, according to Owonaro (1949:19) the Nembe and Kolokuma war occasioned.

One special and significant feature of the riverine diplomacy was the quick restoration of friendship after conflicts. The urgency with which peace was restored after conflict suggests that relations were based on kinship affinities which were imbedded in the traditional method of conflict resolution. The overriding necessity to get back to normal trading relations explains the African concept of warfare and diplomacy.

Dissatisfied with the traditional method of conflict resolution (TDR) that created platform for peace and commerce partly prompted European commercial interests to destroy the Delta middleman. This came without warning, after the Landers in 1830 discovered the outlet of the River Niger. Europeans who sailed up the Niger up to Onitsha and beyond confirmed the commercial significance of the organizational maestro of the Delta middleman in the Niger trade. For example, Dr. Briggs reported to Macgregor Laird that there appeared to be twice much traffic on the Niger as in the upper part of the Rhine (Laird and Oldfield, 1937:165).

Laird himself was much impressed by the extent of commercial activities organized and facilitated by the Delta middleman, especially Nembe in her Niger markets. Also for economic considerations, trading stations were established at the Nembe market spheres such as Aboh, Asaba, Onitsha and Lokoja in 1857. Dr. Baikie's venture became a thorn in the flesh of the Nembe middleman trade in the hinterland. This singular effort broke the camel's back of the Nembe middleman in the Niger Igbo markets.

As if that was not enough, the Europeans traded directly with the hinterland producers who ordinarily would have sold to Delta merchants. The middlemen opposed it as their livelihood depended on their middleman function or role with the hinterland producers. Thus, this exercise, all the more aroused the hostility of the Nembe middleman and her hinterland allies. In other words, the commercially diplomatic friends of the Nembe middleman also opposed the European hinterland movement. It was to curb their excesses that the British gunboats retaliated by bombarding and destroying the allies, as they demonstrated their support for the Nembe middlemanship, by attacking European interests in their domains. A typical example was the fortification of the Niger and attack on Laird's trading ships (Nzimiro, 1972:10). Because the alliance could not be sustained other European merchants also followed Laird's example. Thus it came into full glare when the Royal Niger Company was chartered and became the symbol of European imperialism.

Conclusion

The study has made efforts to investigate the Nembe middleman, with warfare and diplomacy in Pre-colonial Nigeria as the focus. The existence of the middlemen is evident in the mercantile class that transverse the economic zones by creating mechanisms that fed the trade in the Delta. Such mechanisms which include the functions of distribution, organization, regulation as well as facilitating trade between the regions and visiting European overseas traders. Trade was therefore, based on the exchange of specialized items. For example, the salt and fish of the Delta became prized items of trade in the hinterland, while the agricultural items such as yam, livestock, slaves and other valuables of the hinterland fed the Delta populace.

There is no gainsaying that, these arteries of international trade network ante-date the coming of the Europeans on the shores of Nigeria. The geography of Nigeria played significant roles to facilitate the relations, the river system that criss-cross the entire country boosted it, as a result of the Niger and Benue Rivers as well as the Delta created there from. The vehicle of the relations was the canoe needed for mobility and communication. The canoe provided the only means of communication even beyond the Niger to as far as Idah, Rima, Chad Basin etc, where they traded with many Nigerian groups and North Africans and established arteries of relationships (Alagoa, 1970; 319-27). The study therefore established that the Nembe middleman played dominant roles in the Delta trade that many Nigerian groups look up to for leadership. There are, of course, conflicts inherent in the Delta trade.

Because the Delta trade was conducted in such a way that war and peace were built into the structure of the trade in forms such as "falsehood", "double trust" and "chopping of oil". Therefore, the study established that, Nigerians had been engaging in warfare and diplomacy long before the coming of the Europeans. The arrival of the European traders, however, revolutionized warfare and diplomacy in that it shifted away from the traditional time tested rules of 'limited' engagement to the 'large' scale. The Nembe middlemen invasion of Anyama and Otuogidi (1869) is one example of this method; and the invasion of Kaiama (1854) was another to be stressed here.

The study also highlighted that economic considerations exerted European traders to brake the four centuries of Delta middleman trade in the 19th century and established trading stations at the Nembe-Niger Igbo markets as elsewhere. Thus far, the Nembe middleman trade collapsed with the amalgamation and charter of the Royal Niger Company (RNC) that became the symbol of British imperialism in 1886.

References

Primary Sources

A. Bugo (Chief), interviewed June 6, 2002 at Nembe.

Orugbani (Professor of History). Interviewed April 24, 2017 Choba, Port-Harcourt.

Secondary Sources

Adams, J. (1822), *Sketches Taken During Ten Voyages to Africa between the Years 1786 and 1800*, London; Hurst, Robinson & Co.

Alagoa, E.J. (1964/2009), *The Small Brave City State; A History of Nembe- Brass in the Niger Delta*. Madison; University of Wisconsin Press/ Onyoma Research Publications.

----- (1972/2005), *A History of the Niger Delta; An Historical interpretation of Ijo Oral Tradition*. Ibadan; Ibadan University Press/Onyoma Research Publications.

----- (2004), *The uses of Hindsight as Foresight; Reflections on the Niger Delta and Nigerian History*. Port-Harcourt; Onyoma Research Publications.

----- (1999), *The Ijaw Nation in the New Millennium*, Port- Harcourt; Onyoma Research Publications.

Ama-Ogbari, O. (2005), "Twon-Brass in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries; The people, Land and Culture", Ph.D Dissertation, University of Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.

Baikie, W. B. (1856), *Narrative of an Exploring Voyage Up the Rivers Kwara and Benue in 1854*. London; John Murray.

Cookey, J. S. (1986), *King Jaja of the Niger Delta; His Life and Times (1821- 1891)*. New York; Nok Publishers Int'l.

- Dike, K.O. (1956), *Trade and Politics in the Niger Delta 1830-1885; An Introduction to the Economic and Political History of Nigeria*. London; Oxford University Press.
- Ebiwari, D.D. (1988), "A Political History of Ogbia". An unpublished B.A. History Project, University of Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Eferebo, I. (2013), "Nembe and Her Neighbours 1800 to 2008". An unpublished Ph.D Dissertation, University of Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.
- (2002), "Chief Bugo Agala of the Eastern Niger Delta; His Life and Times 1803-1873". An unpublished M.A History Thesis, University of Port-Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Ejituwu, N.C. (1991), *A History of Obolo (Andoni) in the Niger Delta*. Oron; Manson Publishing Company.
- (1992), "Warfare and Diplomacy in the Niger Delta", Falola, T. and Law, R. (eds.), *Warfare and Diplomacy in Pre-colonial Nigeria*, Wisconsin: Wisconsin University Press.
- Enemugwen, J.H. (2000), "The Significance of the Niger Delta Contributions to the Political and Economic Development of Nigeria, 1849-2000". An Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- Owonaro, S.K. (1949), *The History of Ijo (Ijaw) and her Neighbouring Tribes in Nigeria*. Lagos; Niger Printing Works.
- Pereira, P. (1508), *Emeraldo de situ* (trans. G.H.T. Kimble, 1937), London; Hakluyt Society.